

JAINISM, FORGIVENESS AND INCLUSIVITY

Prof. Dr. Hemali Sanghavi

*Head Department of History, K.J. Somaiya College of Arts & Commerce Autonomous,
Mumbai, India. Email: hemali@somaiya.edu*

Paper Received On: 20 NOVEMBER 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 DECEMBER 2025

Published On: 01 JANUARY 2026

Abstract

Religions have been intrinsically built on the sound ecological principles. The basic principles of Jainism show close connection between the religion and ecology. With the contemporary prevalent ecological crises, there is a growing tendency to explore the solutions rooted in the cultural ethos. The paper takes up the ecotheological approach at Jainism. Jainism includes each and every element of universe and considers its intrinsic value. Inclusive and interdependent approach can certainly bring about better and positive outcomes in the world.

Keywords: Jainism, forgiveness, inclusivity

Introduction

Modern world is facing multiple and multilevel crises. The contemporary world presents the complex picture of decline of human values and respect. Stress and environmental crises are ever increasing. Many individuals and organisations around the world are trying to tackle contemporary global issues in their own way. Our ancient heritage of Jain philosophy offers solace for this scenario. Its about making choice to live humbly.

Rational of the study

The Jain teachings are useful and pertinent for the present world. Jains have lived by these values for several millennia. Jainism emphasises on the manifoldness of reality. This understanding and perception can enable us to shape our behavioural pattern. Jain perception is all encompassing.

Objectives

The present study encompasses the Jain perspective towards the universe. It discusses how the Jain perspective has been inclusive of all beings and elements in the world. It thereby presents the solutions for many of the pressing problems of the contemporary world which is in the search of peace. Jain texts emphasis on nonviolence (*Ahimsā*)

Research Methodology

The paper takes up the analytical approach. It derives from ancient knowledge and attempts to connect with the present times. Jain philosophy is unique Indian knowledge system. Traditionally, a Jain adheres to 5 principle vows - non-violence, truthfulness, non-theft, celibacy, and limited possessions.

Scope & Limitations

The paper pertains to the Jain perspective. It looks into the Jain perspective and analyses its implications. Jainism adopts a holistic view of existence.¹ Its world view is not restricted to human beings. It encompasses the tiniest creatures of the universe. Jains maintain that all living beings not just humans have a soul.

Main part of the research

Forgiveness

Forgiveness has been the central theme of Jainism. Every Jain is expected to reflect every day on his actions and ask for forgiveness. This journey enables us to make every day better. Jains accept the existence of different perspectives to truth. Forgiveness also stands for the acceptance of falls and mistakes. It stands for confession and beginning of new , fresh and better beginning. Forgiveness can undo the negativity of the past. Many Jains begin their meals by asking for forgiveness. (*Ksama Yacahna*)²

Maitri Bhavna

Maitri Bhavna is another reflection that the Jain texts talk about. One should have friendship with all living beings. Jain concepts of violence even include wishing ill of another living being. Harm to one is harm to all. Jainism advises the observation of friendliness. It lays stress on the conversations. One should attempt and live with perfect harmony with the nature

¹ Suman Pal, Vinod Kumar, Virendra Kumar, *Scientific Mapping of Global Research Trends on Jain Philosophy: A Bibliometric Analysis*, DOI: 10.5530/jcitation.20250171 accessed on 8 November, 2025.

² Vastupal, Parikh, *Jainism and the New Spirituality*, Toronto, 2006, p.42.

as well as other living beings. One should move from aggressiveness and possessiveness to friendliness. Our different worldviews do not have to bring violence to our lives, instead they can be excellent resources to widen our horizons of understanding.

Jains practice *Samayik* (48 minute meditation) where they are at peace with all living beings. It is the process by which the Jain gets connected with the entire universe. It stands for equanimity. It is the method of attaining peace of mind through self-restraint.

Inclusivity

Jains strive not to cause any harm to the world-plant, animal or human. Jain endeavour to not to harm microorganisms with much caution and energy reflect respect for life. Lives of humblest living beings should be respected.³ Jain belief in incarnation and afterlife also are connected with compassion for all living beings. Present ecological imbalance is product of exclusionary approach of human beings. Jainism treats all living beings equal. It accepts and celebrates diversity which makes the system and the people associated with it resilient. This inclusivity lays down minimalist approach towards the resources.

Parasparō Jivanam

Jainism is based on the dictum of *Parasparō Jivanam*.⁴ It stands for the contention that we are interdependent on each other, the soul renders service to each other. All living beings wish to live. Here all the living beings and forces of nature are included. The phrase is official motto of Jainism. This notion also means that human beings are not centre of the universe. We are just one of the elements. We should not consider ourselves superior to other beings and forces. This false superior notion has resulted in great damage of earth, its resources and smaller beings. Each being and force has its intrinsic value. Human centred view of the world has been disastrous for the environment. After huge damage, we have now shifted to sustainability paradigm. It has been the product of circumstances. We have adopted it in defensive mode.

Conclusion

Jains have a rich history of daily practices and attitudes which demonstrate profound respect for life, including preeminently non-human life. Jainism emphasises on the interconnectedness of life, thereby conserving the nature. Jain lifestyle is marked by

³ *Acharang Sutra* Tr.Hermann Jacobi, Delhi, 1884, 7-1-5.

⁴ Umasvati, *Tattvarthsutra with commentary by Pandit Sukhlalji*, Ahmadabad, 2000, 5-21.

reverence for all living beings. Transition from violent conflicts to peaceful dialogue can boost the common good. Diversity is the strength. This holistic acceptance can make our system resilient. Its about making wiser choice. Transition from a violent to a nonviolent individual or society requires self-discipline and massive shifts in attitudes.

Suggestions and Recommendations

The takeaways of this paper can be used in day today lives. Jainism offers paradigm for contemporary challenges. It encompasses the care and well-being of our immediate universe and recognises the interdependence of humans and their surroundings. *Ahimsā* is the dominant aspect of the Jain practice through which violence free world can be created. Minimum disturbance in the Eco-cycle can contribute to sustainability and diversity. One can get real, subtle solutions through spiritual perspective.

References

Acharang Sutra Tr.Hermann Jacobi, Delhi, 1884.

Long Jeffery, *Jainism A Introduction*, London, 2010.

Rajan, *In Defence of Jain Philosophy and Religion: An Experimental and Comparative Approach Towards Peaceful Culture*”, *Journal of Indian Council of Philosophical Research* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40961-025-00379-y>.

Pal Suman , Kumar, Vinod Kumar Virendra , *Scientific Mapping of Global Research Trends on Jain Philosophy: A Bibliometric Analysis*, DOI: 10.5530/jcitation.20250171 accessed on 8 November, 2025.

Parikh Vastupal, *Jainism and the New Spirituality*, Toronto, 2006.

Umasvati, *Tattvarthsutra with commentary by Pandit Sukhlalji*, Ahmadabad, 2000.